

2025

AfriPlantSci

Research Skills and Modern Breeding
Techniques for Cereals

Summary

The AfriPlantSci 2025 course (17/11 - 28/11) was developed for early career researchers working at institutes in Morocco, Egypt, Kenya, and Pakistan, and was hosted in Morocco by ICARDA, UM6P, and JIC. The primary theme of the course was genome editing in cereals, spanning from construct design to engagement with public policy. The course also explored some connected topics, including gender responsive breeding and the use of online genomics tools. These technical sessions were supplemented with a wide range of workshops aimed at developing participants' core skills, including critical evaluation of literature, engaging presentation of research, responsible use of AI, building collaborative networks, and effective leadership. The activities were showcased through social media posts originating organically from both trainers and participants. Also in the works are a summary video compiled by partners at CABI and a blog produced by the three PIPS interns involved in delivering the course. The participants on the course were universally praised by the trainers as being highly engaged with the material and supportive of each other. In return, the participants were highly positive in their feedback, describing the course as a valuable opportunity for skill development, networking, and exposure to new ways of thinking.

AfriPlantSci 2025 was made possible thanks to:

**Biotechnology and
Biological Sciences
Research Council**

Funding bodies and supporting organisations

Partner institutes

Introduction

AfriPlantSci 2025 was delivered as part of a UK-CGIAR Centre project entitled “Leveraging genetic innovations for accelerated breeding of climate resilient and nutritious crops” ([UK CGIAR Centre](#)). ICARDA was the lead institute and primary CGIAR partner, while JIC was the primary UK partner. The UK-CGIAR Centre aims to support global food security by bringing together scientists from the UK, CGIAR, and Low- or Middle-Income countries (LMICs) to form impact-focused research collaborations. The parent project for AfriPlantSci 2025 aimed to deliver rapid genetic gains in wheat by employing genome editing (GE) to generate novel variation and sequence-based gene discovery to more effectively leverage natural variation. For example, the project’s work package 1 (WP1) explored iron biofortification through GE-mediated mutagenesis directly in elite durum and bread wheat germplasm.

In addition to generating new crop varieties, the project recognised the importance of achieving sustained deployment of those varieties. WP4 was formulated to contribute to successful deployment and thereby improve the project’s potential for impact. Capacity building was deemed a key element of this, as genome-editing crops produced within and for target countries have a higher likelihood of addressing key needs and are viewed more favourably by growers and consumers. The two-week AfriPlantSci 2025 course was formulated as the primary avenue for capacity building within this project. The course built on JIC’s prior experience of running two earlier AfriPlantSci courses (2017 and 2019) in conjunction with CGIAR and NARES partners. Both instances were deemed highly successful by multiple metrics ([AfriPlantSci 2017](#); [AfriPlantSci 2019](#)).

The 2025 course was hosted in Morocco, with participants drawn primarily from ICARDA, the three NARES project partners (ARC, KALRO, and QAU), and University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P). In total, the course welcomed 22 participants from 10 institutes within 5 countries (Figure 1; Figure 2). JIC provided the project management capacity, the bulk of the course trainers, and equipment and reagents, while ICARDA and UM6P were the host institutes for the first and second week of the course, respectively. Training contributions were made by 23 researchers from 11 organisations within 7 countries (Figure 3).

“**THE WAY ... THE TEAM HANDLED EVERYTHING, REALLY HELPED ME ENGAGE WITH EVERYONE AND MEET NEW PEOPLE**”

- FATIMA ZAHRA EL KENDI, PARTICIPANT

Figure 1: Breakdown of AfriPlantSci2025 participants by role

Figure 2: AfriPlantSci2025 participant breakdowns by institute and associated country

Figure 3: Course trainer breakdowns by institute and associated country

Course contents

The course was focused around the technical and core skills required for the successful development and deployment of precision bred varieties. Teaching sessions therefore covered not only the knowledge and techniques required to generate plasmids and transform plants, but also genomics sessions to enable candidate identification, social science to support engagement with public policy mechanisms and gender responsive breeding, and core skills to facilitate effective collaboration, communication, and literature analysis. In addition, six scientific lectures were delivered by senior researchers from the wider UK-CGIAR project to provide real-world context within which to anchor the taught material. The full timetable is provided as [Appendix A](#) at the end of this report.

The course covered the following **skills directly involved in generating GE germplasm**:

- Principles of GE construct design and assembly
- Principles of guide design, transformation, and screening for edits
- A case study on genome editing in wheat targeting the gene GW2
- Principles of advanced genome editing techniques - base editing, prime editing, and HDR
- Pipette handling skills (lab practical)
- PCR (lab practical)
- Gel electrophoresis (lab practical)
- Golden Gate assembly of a GE construct (lab practical)
- E. coli transformation (lab practical)
- Colony PCR (lab practical)
- Plasmid purification (lab practical)
- Analysing Sanger sequencing data with Benchling

Identification of candidate genes and sequences to manipulate is a key prerequisite for any GE project, so the course also provided workshops on **online tools** capable of contributing to this process:

- Using Bioflow, the CGIAR biometrical genetics workflow
- Using Ensembl Plants (computational practical)
- Further wheat bioinformatics resources (computational practical)

At the other end of the pipeline, the course also provided the following social science sessions to provide our participants with **insights into the social and policy** environments required for successful deployment of GE material:

- Gender responsive breeding
- How public policy works
- Panel discussion: sharing policy experiences

Lastly, the course also offered a wide array of workshops aimed at developing the **core skills** necessary for participants to advance their **research careers**:

- Creating and practicing scientific elevator pitches
- Building collaborative networks
- Applying to scientific conferences - writing abstracts and travel grants
- Effective leadership and management
- Communicating science to different audiences
- Refining academic CVs and interview skills
- Ethical use of AI in research
- Critically evaluating scientific papers
- Delivering scientific presentations
- Designing scientific posters

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I GAINED CONFIDENCE IN TALKING ABOUT SCIENCE WITH DIFFERENT AUDIENCES, REALIZED THE IMPORTANCE OF TAILORING EXPLANATIONS, AND IMPROVED MY CV DRAFTING AND INTERVIEW SKILLS, WHICH ARE VALUABLE IN EVERY WALK OF LIFE. THE WORKSHOP ALSO FAMILIARIZED ME WITH POLICY AND HELPED ME UNDERSTAND HOW RESEARCHERS CAN CONTRIBUTE TO POLICY-MAKING

– ANONYMOUS

”

Results

Survey results

The participants responded to anonymous surveys before and immediately after the AfriPlantSci 2025 course to assess their perceived knowledge of particular topics as well as their confidence in the areas covered during the two week course. Overall, 19 of the 22 participants responded to both surveys, providing an impression of the course's impact. All responses were given on a scale of 1-10, where 1 is a low assessment of skillset or confidence and 10 is a high assessment. Another survey will be sent out 6-months post-course which will give a further impression of how actionable and durable the training in the course has been. In the sections below we divide the survey results into two central themes: 'technical capacity' and 'core skills'.

Technical capacity

The course dedicated many of the workshops towards increasing participant understanding of novel techniques, some of which they would put into practice in the lab, and some computationally. Generally, the technical skills of the participants increased following the course, see Figure 4. The average perceived knowledge level about genome editing (GE) in plants before the course was 6.3, which increased to an average of 8.3 post-course (Figure 4A). Similarly, the average perceived understanding of plasmid design and assembly was 5.1, rising to 8.2 post-course (Figure 4B). Overall, confidence in using bioinformatic tools and Sanger sequencing for participants' own research increased to an average of 7.9 (from 6.2; Figure 4C), and 8.4 (also from 6.2; Figure 4D).

As well as the technical skills focused on GE, a key aim of the course was to enhance participant understanding of how regulatory frameworks and legislature applicable to GE are developed. Participants showed a keen interest in how scientists can influence policy even before the course, but this did still increase modestly between the pre-course and post-course surveys (7.7 versus 8.8; Figure 4E). In contrast, participants' understanding of how scientists can influence policy climbed dramatically during the course, shifting from an average confidence level of 5.6 pre-course to 8.3 post-course (Figure 4F). An important aspect of the policy workshops was to enable participants to be able to find, access and understand information regarding policy independently, and so participants were asked how confident they felt finding out about genome editing policy in their own countries as well as others.

The responses showed an increase in confidence from 5.9 pre-course to 8.3 post-course (Figure 4G). The technical and practical skills were of particular interest to participants going into the AfriPlantSci 2025 course. When asked "What are you hoping to gain from connecting with trainers and participants you meet at the workshop?", one participant responded: "I hope to gain deeper technical and practical insights into modern breeding and gene-editing technologies, especially gRNA design, cloning and wheat transformation". The laboratory skills were the focus of the second week of the course. Participants showed an increase in confidence on average on a scale of 1-10 from an average of 8.3 to an average of 9.5 (Figure 4H).

Overall, these findings indicate that the technical capacity of participants increased as a result of the AfriPlantSci 2025 course, both in molecular and bioinformatic techniques, and in their understanding of policy development.

Figure 4. Violin plots showing results from pre- and post-course surveys of participants' confidence and knowledge levels regarding the technical and laboratory based skills covered in the course. Participants were asked to score their perceived knowledge (A&B), interest (E) and confidence levels (C, D, F, G, H) on a scale of 1-10 where 1 is no knowledge/interest/confidence and 10 is expert/very interested/very confident.

Core skills

The surveys also provide strong evidence for improvements in participants' core skills (Figure 5). When asked how confident they feel presenting their professional skills in a CV or in a job interview, initially the average confidence levels were 6.8 and 6.7, respectively. This increased for participants post-course, averaging 9.4 and 9.2 respectively (Figure 5A and Figure 5B). Prior to the course, 54.5% of participants who completed the pre-course survey had not applied to travel grants before. Participants also gained confidence in this area, with an average pre-course response of 5.9 versus an average post-course confidence of 8.8 (Figure 5C). The 6-month post-course survey will follow-up on this and ask whether development of this skill has been acted upon.

Similarly, communication skills developed, with participants' confidence in communicating their own science to other scientists, as well as non-scientists, increasing from 7.5 and 7.8, to 9.3 and 9.1 respectively (Figure 5D). Leadership workshops were designed to improve participants' confidence and ability in leading groups of people. This increased from 7.1 to 8.8, showing an increase in participant capacity for leadership. Despite 87% of participants using generative AI in their research, participant confidence in understanding the effective use of generative AI was on average 6.6. This increased to 9.1 post-course and participant confidence using generative AI will be further assessed in the 6-months post-course survey.

AfriPlantSci 2025 placed strong emphasis on improving the networking skills of participants. Participants increased their confidence talking to scientists outside of their research group in networking settings, such as at a conference, from 7.4 on average, to 8.7. Only 21.7% of participants prior to the course had 15+ connections outside of their own institute, which increased to 45.5% following extensive networking throughout the course. A crucial aspect of networking is maintaining connections following initial meetings. Generally, confidence in this skill also increased, from an average of 7.0 to 8.5. Forming collaborations was an important consideration for participants before the course, with one individual stating: "I hope to connect with others, learn from their experiences and build strong collaborative relationships that may open opportunities for us to work together in the future". This appears to have been achieved, with average confidence in initiating scientific collaborations increasing from an average of 6.4 pre-course to an average of 8.0.

Figure 5. Violin plots showing results from pre- and post-course surveys of participants' confidence and knowledge levels regarding the core and professional skills covered in the course. Participants were asked to score their confidence levels on a scale of 1-10 where 1 is no confidence and 10 is very confident.

Networking and collaboration

The number of connections outside of the participants' institute rose. By the end of the course 95% of participants felt they had 5 or more connections outside of their institute (compared to 68% pre-course). The number with 15+ connections rose from 26% to 40%.

During interviews, trainers frequently commented on the importance of international networks in their careers, including Valentine Ntui, (UM6P) who said *"collaborating with professors, scientists, industry, companies, will actually help to sharpen their careers ... When we write proposals, we do not write alone, we write in collaboration with other scientists ... As a scientist, we cannot know everything, you only know something in your areas, but you need other areas to build up to something"*. It's Michael Baum's (ICARDA) view that forming international networks *"was part of [his] education from the beginning"* and one participant nicely underpinned this idea by describing that *"engaging with the trainers and other participants helped .. broaden [their] perspectives"*. We aimed to build a close cohort where the participants felt comfortable to share with and learn from each other.

When asked **"What have you gained/learned from engaging with the course trainers and other participants?"**, a common theme was the *"supportive network"* participants had felt they had gained. Feedback stated that they had *"gained confidence in talking with different people"* and that they enjoyed *"sharing knowledge with colleagues"*. This feedback captures the open and collaborative environment that was achieved during this workshop. A six month or one year post-course follow up would help quantify how many of these connections will result in formal collaborations, but for now, the new, supportive network that was built here can be viewed as a major success of the AfriPlantSci 2025 workshop.

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“THIS COURSE IS VERY IMPORTANT FOR PARTICIPANTS AS WE HAVE A VERY DIVERSE RANGE OF PARTICIPANTS, FROM KENYA, EGYPT ETC, AND IT WILL GIVE THEM A GREAT PLATFORM TO LEARN FROM THIS WIDE RANGE OF RESEARCHERS, AND NOT ONLY THE CORE SKILLS ... BUT ALSO THE SOFT SKILLS”

– PROF. AWAIS RASHEED, TRAINER

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Mutual learning exchange

The trainers from the UK (JIC, UEA, and NISD) commented that attending the course increased their knowledge of Global South research. This included what species are of regional importance in Morocco and partner nations, the capacities of - and challenges faced by - partner institutes, and the very strong focus on applied research within Global South plant science, including reciprocal interactions with farmers.

Dr Nikolai Adamski:

“I was fascinated by how many different crops a given research group works on. Every project is tackling very specific issues that affect farmers, with a focus on biotic and abiotic stress tolerance / resistance.”

Dr Matt Heaton:

“I gained a greater sense of the interest across African early career researchers in engaging more with social and political spaces beyond academic [ones], with the hope of increasing impact from their research.”

Dr Anne Edwards:

“The participants’ eagerness to learn and collaborate was deeply inspiring, while the desert landscape stood as a powerful, ever-present reminder of the environmental challenges confronting African agriculture.”

Social media deliverables

The AfriPlantSci2025 course aims to leave a media footprint in order to promote the success of the students, trainers, and workshop alike. LinkedIn posts from trainers and participants throughout and following the course have already produced a slew of engagement from people's wider networks, and many were reposted by partners institutes' official accounts.

Interview footage, as well as clips of site visits and laboratory practicals, will be edited into a long-format video which highlights the positive outcomes of the course and emphasises the importance of precision breeding training for research autonomy in Global South countries. This video will be edited by CABI, one of the course's partner organisations. The interview footage will also be released in short-format videos, providing direct insights into the aspects of the course that stood out for particular participants. In the development of these videos for social media, an archive of B-roll footage was established which can be accessed for future promotional use for UK-CGIAR Centre projects. The footage encompasses laboratory practicals, collaborative group activities, lectures (on both technical and core skills), and a visit to a smallholder (cactus) farm.

Furthermore the three PIPS students (Kestrel Maio, Ella Penny and Samuel Matthew Shackleton-Chavez) have written blogs for their PhD funders, the Norwich Research Park Doctoral Training Partnership, as well as for the John Innes Centre website, these will be uploaded permanently to display their contributions to the course, as well as inspiration for future PhD internships with Norwich Research Park.

Opportunities for improvement

Overall, the AfriPlantSci 2025 course had a very positive reception from the participants - in both the formal pre- and post-course surveys and in more informal feedback, both verbal and written, throughout the course. Nonetheless, we have identified several areas for improvement that organisers of future AfriPlantSci courses may wish to take into consideration. For example, a recurrent theme was a desire for bioinformatics training, which we consider in more detail below.

Feedback from participants

As described above, the course addressed a wide range of **core career skills** and our surveys suggest there were marked improvements in confidence and ability related to these skills. However, we did receive an interesting suggestion for a further career skill to include; proposal and project writing. This could very well be included in future installments of AfriPlantSci and would certainly benefit post-doctoral researchers aiming to develop independent research programmes. In 2025, though, the majority of attendees (15/22) were at earlier career stages, so such a topic may not have been relevant for a sufficient proportion of our audience. On the other hand, it could be argued that all researchers should have some exposure to the mechanisms and skills of funding acquisition. At the least, this can help researchers understand if leading a research group is a career pathway they wish to pursue.

On the **technical side**, we received a request for further theory on alternative genome editing technologies. We covered CRISPR-Cas9 mutagenesis plus some derivatives including base editing, prime editing, and HDR, but the particular request we received suggested we should additionally include material on TALENs and ZFNs. While these could receive a cursory mention, a detailed lecture on these tools may not be an appropriate use of course time given that they are rapidly obsolescing. As an alternative, we suggest that a future course could include some material on RNAi. Though not a GE method, it is a highly complementary research tool that would serve to broaden the scope of the course. There was also a suggestion of teaching a qPCR protocol in the future, which was unfortunately not possible for a group of this size in the facilities we had access to.

Data analysis and statistics were also raised multiple times as additional topic of interest. As summarised succinctly by one participant: "I would have loved if the training included ... data analysis or statistical analysis". Another expressed a desire to "work directly with real datasets".

However, by far the most requested training area by the participants was **bioinformatics**. This came up in the post-course survey, on written notes during our revision and reflection session, and in spoken accounts. The course did deliver training on online genomics tools, primarily Bioflow and Ensembl Plants, but we did not include any material on coding skills. Participant quotes on the topic include requests for "basics of bioinformatics" and "basics of bioinformatics and Bioflow", as well as a more detailed piece of feedback: "I would have appreciated an additional component focusing on hands-on bioinformatics for plant pathology, especially in genome assembly, variant analysis, or microbial community profiling for wheat diseases". Interest in the practical use of AlphaFold was

feedback suggests there is sufficient interest in these partner organisations for a future training course whose technical material is dedicated to bioinformatics training. It is increasingly valuable for wet lab scientists and agronomists to have a working knowledge of R and shell coding so that they can execute certain analyses independently and communicate effectively with bioinformatician colleagues.

Feedback from trainers

For this course we adopted a simple model for participant recruitment, which was to let project partners at ICARDA, UM6P, and the NARES nominate people for the course. The aim of this approach was to lower administrative burden versus an open application format and to allow partners to select researchers they believed would remain in-country or within the Global South to boost the capacity-building impact of the course. However, a result of this format was a wide range in the participants' pre-course knowledge of GE theory and molecular biology skills, owing to their differing scientific backgrounds. We found that the participants were highly supportive of each other when areas of weaker knowledge arose and seeing this was in fact a highlight for many of the trainers. Nonetheless, a more uniform **knowledge level** may have been more efficient, either allowing the course to take plenty of time on the fundamentals, or to focus on more advanced theory and laboratory skills. Achieving a participant pool with more equal prior knowledge could be achieved with a stricter, more focused brief to project partners if a nomination approach is taken or by returning to an open application model.

We also identified that there was insufficient preparation for **religious and cultural considerations**. Notably, some participants were unable to attend some dinners during the first week due to alcohol being served on the venues' premises. Secondly, there were several moments during the course where handshakes were exchanged (for example, upon participants receiving their course certificates) and it would have been beneficial for trainers to know ahead of time that some female participants would not shake hands with a male trainer. This would have allowed trainers to ask whether the participant was comfortable shaking hands rather than assuming they would be, or for a female trainer to have taken on that role.

Lastly, something raised during the project manager's initial networking trip to Morocco in July was whether time for prayers needed to be accounted for in the programme. At the time, project partners

in Morocco suggested this would not be expected or needed. However, during the course itself, we found that trainers and participants from Egypt and Pakistan did require time for prayers on Fridays (the holiest day of the week in Islam). This highlights the need to actively engage with all stakeholders. We were able to partially accommodate this during week 1 by rearranging sessions, but were unable to in week 2. We suggest that the pre-course survey for the next AfriPlantSci course should include specific questions on religious and cultural requirements to prevent such issues arising in the future and to ensure all participants and trainers feel comfortable and welcomed.

stakeholders. We were able to partially accommodate this during week 1 by rearranging sessions, but were unable to in week 2. We suggest that the pre-course survey for the next AfriPlantSci course should include specific questions on religious and cultural requirements to prevent such issues arising in the future and to ensure all participants and trainers feel comfortable and welcomed.

Regarding **facilities**, we experienced issues with WiFi access while at UM6P, as it appeared their guest WiFi only worked for those with Moroccan phone numbers. This required several sessions to run without online components (e.g. 'Mentimeter' quizzes) or for participants to work in groups. If possible, future courses should allow time for one or more trainers to test and troubleshoot site facilities before the course begins and a back-up venue (e.g. a second conference room) should be booked in case of technical failures. A less serious issue, but one worth considering, is that the conference room at UM6P had poor lighting, making event photography much more challenging.

Catering was largely well-received and dietary requirements were largely able to be addressed, with some difficulties for vegetarian trainers in week 2 when we ate in a UM6P campus cafeteria. However, both participants and trainers noted that, during week 1, the lunches and dinners were frequently far too large, leading to considerable food waste. This appeared to be a cultural norm required for good hospitality as our Moroccan colleagues were not surprised by it. However, it may be worth being more firm with catering staff and restaurants about portion size in the future given the direct relevance of food security to our work and how uncomfortable it made some people feel.

The three **PIPS students** were closely involved in the entire two-week course, plus its prior preparations and follow-up work. While, overall, they enjoyed their involvement, they suggested that specific efforts be made to highlight the intensity and duration of the required contact time to any trainers involved in the full span of such a course. This could enable them to better prepare both

logistically and mentally. If possible, 'full-time' course trainers should be given one or two evenings 'off' for recovery during the course, though this may not be feasible for the overall course organiser / project manager.

Finally, the strategy for delivery of **social media content** was too slow to achieve immediate impact. For example, trainers captured interviews of over 15 trainers and participants, but, as of three weeks post-course, no video content has been released online. Our plan was not to create specific AfriPlantSci 2025 social media accounts as these often have poor reach due to being new accounts and have poor longevity. Instead, we aimed to release posts on partner organisations' official accounts to reach wider networks (while maintaining a brand identity using a consistent hashtag: #AfriPlantSci2025). However, we encountered resistance from multiple organisations' social media teams as they were not sold on the merits of our planned content. One suggested that they would prefer to repost material from personal accounts to achieve an "authentic voice". However, we note that this places an unfair burden on the trainers to use their personal social media accounts to promote AfriPlantSci. For example, trainers may wish to release one or two posts about their involvement in the course on LinkedIn, but a daily blog post would likely just come across as inauthentic. We suggest returning to the prior approach of using specific AfriPlantSci social media accounts (primarily LinkedIn and Instagram) and requesting institute accounts to repost these. An 'authentic voice' could still be achieved by doing account 'takeovers' by different trainers for a few days at a time. This has previously been exemplified well on social media accounts run by the UK cereals conference 'Monogram'.

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“DEVELOPING A 2 WEEK TRAINING COURSE IS A LOT OF WORK, THERE ARE A LOT OF DIFFERENT ASPECTS WHICH GO INTO A TRAINING WORKSHOP WHICH I HADN'T CONSIDERED BEFORE TAKING THIS PLACEMENT, WE HAVE BEEN TAKING A LOT OF DIFFERENT ROLES... MANAGING ALL OF THESE DIFFERENT ROLES HAS BEEN A CHALLENGE BUT ALSO VERY REWARDING”

– KESTREL MAIO, TRAINER (PIPS)

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Future perspectives

The AfriPlantSci 2025 course largely ran smoothly without major technical issues, our impact surveys suggest positive results on participant knowledge and core skill development, and most participants anticipate they will have positive future engagements with each other and course trainers. Here, we highlight several aspects which we believe contributed to these successes and should be integrated into future AfriPlantSci courses.

The **pre- and post-course surveys** were an essential tool in designing and measuring the outcomes of this course. We highly recommend that future organisers implement such surveys, being sure to include specific quantitative questions as well as calls for longer-form written feedback.

We found that it was highly beneficial to dedicate a sizeable portion of the first day to interactive core skills sessions for ice breaking and easing people into the course. This helped develop **camaraderie within the cohort** and facilitated everyone taking part in later group activities with more confidence. This was further assisted by ensuring that as many trainers and participants as possible ate meals together throughout the two weeks. Several evening social events occurred organically while we were at UM6P during the second week, including bowling, beach volleyball, and board games. Multiple participants described the friendliness of the other participants and trainers as a positive highlight of the course.

We found that having trainers and participants who traveled from multiple countries (Morocco, Egypt, Kenya, Pakistan, China and the UK) led to curiosity and many interesting conversations. Trainers and participants alike wanted to hear about each others' life experiences, their work, and how genome editing policy functions in their countries of residence. Overall, we were able to foster a positive and inclusive atmosphere that energised our attendees and encouraged **strong participation**.

We suggest that future courses retain a strong focus on **capturing photo and video material**, as we have found that many participants have requested these for their CVs and LinkedIn profiles as visual evidence of the training received. The physical course certificates were also well received for similar reasons.

On the taught content of the course, we found that **switching between sessions on technical and core skills** (rather than having them in separate blocks) was positively received, with collaborative core skill activities serving to re-energise participants for the more technical sessions. We found that not dedicating full days to one topic (such as just on laboratory skillsxs) were beneficial, as participants could have a change of pace and mental focus, especially as participants came into the course with different goals in mind - some more focused on the lab, theory, policy, or career skills.

Overall, it was a pleasure to run this course given the exceptional engagement and warmth of the participants. We hope our suggestions and reflections can contribute to running an equally enjoyable and successful AfriPlantSci course in the future.

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“THERE IS A REAL ELEMENT OF EXCITEMENT IN THE ROOM... WE CAN NURTURE A REALLY PROMISING SET OF INDIVIDUALS FAR INTO THEIR CAREER IN THE FUTURE, I HOPE THAT AFTER THESE TWO WEEKS AND AFTER MY TIME FINISHES HERE, THIS WONT BE THE END, THIS WILL CARRY ON”

– MATT HEATON, TRAINER

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“ENGAGING WITH THE TRAINERS AND OTHER PARTICIPANTS HELPED ME BROADEN MY PERSPECTIVES. I LEARNED PRACTICAL SKILLS FROM THEIR EXPERIENCE, GAINED NEW IDEAS FROM OUR DISCUSSIONS, AND IMPROVED MY ABILITY TO WORK COLLABORATIVELY. FINALLY, IT GAVE A ME SUPPORTIVE NETWORK THAT WILL CONTINUE TO INSPIRE AND CHALLENGE ME.”

- ANONYMOUS

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WEEK 2	Sunday (23rd)	Monday (24th)	Tuesday (25th)	Wednesday (26th)	Thursday (27th)	Friday (28th)	Saturday (29th)
09:00-11:00	Marrakesh guided tour	Introduction to UM6P and site tour	Pipette handling skills	Assembly of a wheat genome editing construct	Colony PCR	Plasmid purification	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers.
11:00-11:30			Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
11:30-12:30	Marrakesh guided tour	Lunch	Gel electrophoresis	Scientific lecture: Valentine Otang Ntui	Colony PCR	Sample preparation for plasmid Sanger sequencing	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers.
12:30-13:15			Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	
13:15-14:15	Marrakesh guided tour	Guide design, transformation, and screening for edits	Scientific lecture: Susanne Dreisgacker	<i>E. coli</i> transformation - heat shock and recovery	Get Genome presents: don't clone alone, ensure your vectors are verified	Group activity: revision and reflection	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers.
14:15-15:15			Additional genome editing techniques	Analysing Sanger sequencing data with Benchling	ensure your vectors are verified	AfriPlantSci 2025 closing ceremony	
15:15-15:30	Marrakesh guided tour	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers.
15:30-16:30			Genome editing in wheat: case study on GW2	Presenting scientific research	Group activity: designing scientific posters	Get Genome presents: don't clone alone, ensure your vectors are verified	
16:30-20:00	Free time	Group activity: critically evaluating scientific papers	Free time	<i>E. coli</i> transformation=plating	Free time	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers.
17:30-19:30			Free time	Free time	Free time		
19:30-20:30	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner		

Key: ● Core skills workshop ● Cultural activity ● Laboratory practical ● Lecture ● Technical workshop

Appendix A: schedule

Key: ● Core Skills workshop ● Cultural activity ● Laboratory practical ● Lecture ● Technical workshop

WEEK 1	Sunday (16th)	Monday (17th)	Tuesday (18th)	Wednesday (19th)	Thursday (20th)	Friday (21st)	Saturday (22nd)
09:00-11:00		Welcome, meeting the cohort, and creating your elevator pitch	Gender responsive breeding	Bioflow: an integrated pipeline for quality control and genetic analysis in modern breeding	Effective leadership and management	Refining academic CVs and interview skills	
11:00-11:30		Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
11:30-12:30		Group activity: sharing science in small groups	How policy works	Scientific lecture: James Karaija	Group activity: communicating science to different audiences	Continued	
12:30-13:15		Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Scientific lecture: Awais Rasheed	Travel to Ben Guerir and visit to a smallholder cactus farm
13:15-15:15	Arrival to ONOMO Rabat Terminus Hotel for international and UM6P participants and trainers	Introduction to the UK-CGIAR Centre project and Diane Saunders lecture	Panel discussion: sharing policy experiences	Using the Ensembl Plants database	Construct design and assembly	Lunch	
15:15-15:30		AfriPlantSci 2025 course overview	Building collaborative networks	Coffee break	Coffee break	Scientific lecture: Ahmed Elkot	
15:30-16:30		Coffee break	Coffee break	Further wheat bioinformatics resources	Coffee break	Coffee break	
16:30-17:30		Introduction to ICARDA and site tour	Group activity: applying to scientific conferences	Group activity: applying to scientific conferences	Networking at British Ambassador's residence	Responsible use of AI	
17:30-21:00		Return to accommodation and dinner	Return to accommodation and dinner	Return to accommodation and dinner	Return to accommodation and dinner	Return to accommodation and dinner	Arrival at UM6P accommodation and dinner

Appendix B: list of participants and trainers

Name	Organisation and Country of Work	Email	Photograph	
Trainers	Achaimaa Mdini	University Mohammed VI Polytechnic, Morocco	achaimaa.mdini@um6p.ma	
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	Angela Payne	John Innes Centre, UK	angela.payne@jic.ac.uk	
	Dr Anna Backhaus	IPK, Germany	backhaus@ipk-gatersleben.de	
	Dr Anne Edwards	John Innes Centre, UK	anne.edwards@jic.ac.uk	

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	Prof. Diane Saunders OBE	John Innes Centre, UK	diane.saunders@jic.ac.uk	
	Dr Dina Najjar	ICARDA, Morocco	d.najjar@cgiar.org	
	Ella Penny	John Innes Centre, UK	eleanor.penny@jic.ac.uk	
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